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Research Article

PEREVALANCE OF MALARIA IN LAHORE: A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY HELD IN MAYO HOSPITAL LAHORE¹Dr. Bakhtawar Fatima, ²Dr Aiman Khan, ³Dr. Samina Javed¹BHU Phama Sarai, Tehsil Nowshera Virkan, Gujranwala²Federal Government Polyclinic (PGMI)³THQ Hospital Murree**Article Received:** July 2020**Accepted:** August 2020**Published:** September 2020**Abstract:**

Malaria is a disease that is caused by bites of mosquito. Malaria is a very spreading disease in all over the world also in Pakistan. Different tests conducted to diagnose this disease. Test also conducted in Lahore or all over the Pakistan on different people of age pregnant and non-pregnant females living in urban and rural area as well. 1000 tests had conducted in 11% male 7% non-pregnant females and 8% pregnant females suffering from this disease. Patients show different signs like fever headache vomiting. Mostly malaria spreading in rural areas where proper sewerage system is not exist water standing at unpaved streets due to which new mosquitos born. It is also observed that it infects poor and middle class people who do not afford anti mosquitos.

Key Words: Malaria, unpaved conditions, rural areas, developing countries, pregnant females

Corresponding author:**Dr Bakhtawar Fatima,**

BHU Phama Sarai, Tehsil Nowshera Virkan, Gujranwala

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INTRODUCTION:

Malaria is a disease that is caused by bites of mosquitos is a life taking disease that covered whole world as well as Pakistan [1]. Mostly it effects under developed countries. It also affects animals that are caused by in-balance of chemicals. It is caused by bite of female mosquito when female mosquito bite the saliva entered in blood and passes to the liver [2]. Symptoms include head ache and illness. When patient effects from malaria it leads to death or coma [3]. The spreading of malaria in Asia region is very complex. Malaria spreading in most those areas where the environment is friendly for mosquito's interaction [4]. On many factors the spreading of mosquito depends like unpaved streets land use structure of house. In ancient times malaria is a disease that is caused to death [5]. Malaria cases reported from world are 550000 which also include cases from Pakistan. Malaria spreading in different genders pregnant and non-pregnant females spreading of malaria is most in rural areas [6]. The chances of spreading of malaria in pregnant females are most which effect female and her baby as well [7].

METHODOLOGY:

We collected different blood sample depends on their gender pregnancy and non- pregnancy also of different age groups. Total 1000 blood sample were collected in which 400 are males 300 are non-pregnant females and 300 are pregnant females. Samples collected from urban and rural areas from Lahore. Then send them to a clinic for further reports blood sample place on a glass slide and made thick and thin layers. Further the sample studied through microscope to find the tests are negative or positive.

RESULTS:

Total 1000 test will be conducted from which 400 samples are from male 300 from non -pregnant females and 300 are pregnant females which are from rural and urban are from Lahore we say that samples will be taken from different area from Lahore. Bio-data information will be taken through form filling and question answer session. Form includes point age gender and pregnancy points to be filled. Results are shocking we found that in non-pregnant females 22 samples show malaria parasite 19 suffer from *P. vivex* and 4 suffer from *P. falciparum* infection. From 400 males 35 are caused from malaria 30 shows *P. vivex* and 10 suffer from *P. falciparum*. Pregnant females 25 are positive for malaria and 25 shows *P. vivex* and *P. falciparum*. Malaria also spreading in different months from April to July 32 positive cases for male come 2 cases were seen in April and 14 cases were seen in June and 16 cases were seen I July. Likewise pregnant women 4 cases were seen in April 10 seen in May 12 seen in July. Likewise

non-pregnant females 15 cases are seen in April 5 seen in May 2 seen in June. These values obtained by chi square test. The tests were divided into 5 age groups (6-18 , 19-27 , 29-37 , 39-49 and above 50.it seems that in males case 12 , 9, 6 , 3, 3 cases were belong to 1st 2nd 3rd 4th and 5th group. Also in case of pregnant females 5, 8 ,3 ,2,4 were belong to 1st 2nd 3rd 4th and 5th group. The sewerage system and hygienic condition is also concerned in which we observe that among positive cases of male 34% do not have proper system of sewerage. In case of female 38 % don't have proper system of sewerage. Among positive pregnant females in which 58 % do not have proper system of sewerage. Usage of anti -mosquito also effect these things in which we observe that 38 % use anti-mosquito while others do not use. 47% of non-pregnant females use anti mosquito while other do not use. 62 % of pregnant female use anti mosquito while other do not use. Blood pressure also observed at that time in which we observed that 8 males have high blood pressure and others have normal pressure. In case of pregnant female 32 % have high blood pressure while others have normal blood temperature. In case of non-pregnant females 22% have high blood pressure while others have normal blood pressure. Areas are also main factor in which we observed that in male case 52% belong to rural areas while others are from urban. In case of pregnant females 62% belongs to rural while others from urban. In case of mom-pregnant females 55% are from rural areas while others are from urban. Employment status will also be observed in which we studied that in case of males 59% are employed while others are un-employed and student. In case of pregnant females 62% are employed while others are un-employed and student. In case of non-pregnant females 20% are employed while others are un-employed and student. Those have collected with fully passion. Income status will also be considered that is divided into 4 groups 1st group is 1000-10000 2nd group is 10000-20000 3rd group is 20000-30000 and 4th group is 30000-40000 . In case of pregnant females we observed that 32%, 12%, 9%,4%are from 1st 2nd 3rd 4th group respectively. In case of non-pregnant we observed that 31%, 12%, 6%,7%are from 1st 2nd 3rd 4th group respectively. In case of males we observed that 87%, 22%, 6%,37%are from 1st 2nd 3rd 4th group respectively. Patient shows different symptoms like fever headache vomiting we observed that all males have fever. In the case of pregnant females all have fever. In the case of non-pregnant females all have fever. Mostly shows head ache and vomiting but some don't shows.

DISCUSSION:

In our decade mostly malaria controlled in all our the world also in Pakistan [8]. 47% malaria had been controlled in various age groups[9]. From

2000 to 2013 48 % malaria had been controlled. 5 million malaria deaths had been reported in this decade. 66 countries that suffers from malaria will meet millennium development goals to reduce malaria and to over -come this tragedy 57 countries are on their way to reduce it [10]. By the efforts of who 77% malaria had been controlled in 2015 [11]. Our results shows the spreading of area in Lahore different factors like temperature land use will be considered in this way [12]. Our studied also shows that it also effect family condition. Low income group have low spreading while other are high [13]. We also shows that blood pressure also effects on it high blood pressure have low malaria while others have high. It also shows that malaria is spreading in rural area where un-hygienic conditions available [14]. We also observed that spreading of malaria is low in those who use anti mosquito [15]. It means that anti mosquitos perform well. It is also found that malaria is spreading in month of June when rains starts and water stays in street [16]. The spreading of malaria are most in pregnant females because of many reason like lowness of immunity system increasing chances of illness [17]. Malaria effects new born baby like abortion or still birth etc. If mother will be suffering from malaria then it will also affect on baby and after baby birth he or she will have symptoms of malaria and in some cases death occurs [18].

CONCLUSION:

We observed that malaria is spreading in rainy time. We also observed that malaria is spreading in rural and back-word area. It I also observed that anti mosquito works good to prevent the spreading of malaria. Pregnant females have more chances of malaria because of its immune system and have high chances of fever. We must use anti mosquito and clean our environment so that we also take part in to stop spreading of malaria.

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